

could face. This is the first time this text becomes openly available to the English audience – the few studies featuring it are in languages other than English and difficult/expensive to obtain.

This document pursues the main aim of listing the principal expenses, including all the unique cases and showing the range of expenditure that the Bishop allowed himself. The task of determining the explicit structure of expenditure will require tabulating the entire document in the form of an even larger Excel spreadsheet than I have produced for the present publication – something I may undertake do in the future.

The help in understanding the more challenging Latin entries provided by Rich Price is gratefully acknowledged – his long experience in translation was more than useful. Likewise, Carlo Niato is gratefully acknowledged for helping locate a full transcription of the accounts which was used in this study: https://play.google.com/books/reader?id=ZEOJAAAAQAAJ&pg=GBS.RA2-PA90&hl=it&fbclid=IwAR0upIwHpAyH3nKBbCxyLqgqVqloGlrF_mzmcIgbkWO25aqNB1WljvpMVFo

[Image on the first page: 1215-1230 Germany, BSB Clm 17401 – the Scheyern book of matins]

2. INTRODUCTION

The reader of this article will be mainly interested in the practical aspects of Bishop Wolfger's travels and this may be satisfied with superficial review of the background. In 1202, Wolfger von Erla was summoned to Rome to appear before the Pope and be held to answer for certain accusations of misbehaviour on his side. He had nothing else to do than submit to the order and depart to Rome in 1203, to return to Austria and Germany in the middle of 1204. However as we will see, his expenses show that he did not give himself to guilt – on the contrary, he had some damned good time in his journey!

This article uses the *denarius* (d) as the price unit and avoids the use of shilling and talent/pound, for the sake of ease of reading and understanding of the expenses. The “long” shilling (=30d) and the “short” shilling, or simply shilling (=12d), as well as the talent (*talentum* = 240d) and the mark (160d) are mentioned in the translated list of prices, as they appear in the original entries.

Fig. 1. Itinerary of Bishop Wolfger von Erla on his way to and from Rome in 1203-1204. Adapted from Max Resch, *Die Reise des Passauer Bischofs Wolfger von Erla durch Italien / The Journey of the Bishop of Passau Wolfger von Erla through Italy* (2019).

As apparent from Figure 1, the Bishop visited several tens of locations during his travels. This road trip was well documented on several parchment sheets, presenting a dry list of expenses and sums that lack a narrative component. However, in their meticulousness, these records are extremely valuable to us as they offer a rare unbiased view of the everyday reality in which the medieval characters lived (and prospered, as in the case of Wolfger!)

Fig. 2. Bishop Wolfger's personal seal, still attached to an authentic document of 1216, https://inlibris.com/item/bn53041/?fbclid=IwAR3e_oA4YID994NvVPUw9I9IEdyBeCPrExuMV04mQsNdK8DLUmDXt2sw-UA.

3. CLASSIFICATION OF THE EXPENSES

The recorded travel expenses can be divided into several broad categories which will be discussed separately:

- Gifts
- Purchases
- Daily expenses: services, maintenance, repair, necessities
- Messengers
- Performers

The purchases were recorded twice in the original, first in the order of occurrence, and then rewritten again with an attempt to classify and order them. However, this original ordering does not increase clarity sufficiently for our research purposes, so I have completely rearranged them per the above categories, and further by type of item or service.

3.1 Gifts

Any travel was definitely seen by the nobles as a PR opportunity. The primary tool to promote oneself was to distribute gifts as much as possible – expecting that the receivers would spread the word about the giver's generosity. Wolfger was no different, and his accounts testify to very active giving. He made sure to spread his budget across the entire social spectrum, from the poor and wretched to the lords and officials. These gifts are recorded personally as distinct from alms, implying that each gift receiver, even if poor and unremarkable, probably had the honour of an audience with the bishop, while the distribution of alms were not as personal. The gifts, nevertheless, grow exponentially with the importance of the subject. There is so much consistency there that one can't help but wonder whether they used an established scale. Poor commoners received 2-6d per person; poor clerics, scholars and low-tier officials 30-120d per person; priests, knights and important servants, such as a steward - about 240d (1 talent), while lords, old friends and other greater persons were given sums ranging from 300d to 9600d.

One surprising feature is how specific the scribe was in describing the receivers – and for what purpose, if not for the sake of remembering the details of the journey? The records explicitly mention “a naked boy“, “a bald apostate from Ensdorf“, “two Frenchmen“, “a poor crusader from Normandy“ “a nun from Eboracum“, “knight Heinrich the Swabian“, “a blond Saxon in black clothes“, “a poor crusader from Normandy“, and “a fat Saxon scholar wearing black clothes“, “the old bloodletter of the duke Luipold“ and “cellarer, an old friend of the bishop“. Wolfger von Erla had sure had his share of memorable encounters!

3.2 Purchases

One very valuable feature of the accounts is the evidence of active purchasing. The bishop apparently went shopping wherever good options presented themselves – probably in person to the more prominent merchants, but sending his servants to buy from lesser merchants, and possibly receiving them at his accommodations. So many items are found in the accounts that we will need to review them per category.

3.2.1 Accessories

Knives, gloves, bags (belt purses, bigger bags for money and bags for spices) and belts appear several times. A simple knife was bought for 3d. Belt bags for keeping money and small items (*bursa*) were purchased several times, mentioned in plural at 5d and 7d – much cheaper than a single bag as bought for 24d, implying varying quality and level of decoration. Belts were either cheap (3d, a plain leather belt for brother Heinrich), midrange (72d for two belts, those of the butler and brother Heinrich) or expensive (384d for two silken belts for Wolfger).

3.2.2 Shoes

Basic shoes were available starting from 3 pennies, as documented in some sources (e.g. bishop Wolfger's travel accounts of 1203-1204, where shoes costing 3,4 or 5 pennies are documented, once specifically bought for a servant). Using cheap shoes such as these would be preferable for peasants, labourers and soldiers. It seems unreasonable for these categories to use chausses with textile or even leather sole, both of which are certainly less resistant to wear than even basic shoes; moreover, shows add protection for the foot useful for these professions. More senior followers of the bishop had boots worth 12, 18, 19, 26, 29 pennies, while the Bishop himself those at 62 pennies. Even shoe grease (*pingui pro calciis*) was purchased for 8d. Riding leggings (*ocreas*), probably of leather, were estimated to cost 6d (an allowance given to messenger from Zahringen).

3.2.3 Clothing

Clothing was purchased for the Bishop and the members of his retinue during the trip, in replacement of the old ones or simply as a whim. A few gifts were also given with a direct specification that they were intended for the purchase of clothing, revealing the anticipated prices.

Gloves. These were generally cheap, only 4d even for the bishop himself – probably plain leather riding gloves. Falconry gloves worth 6d, 8d and 51d are also recorded – these were bigger, required better leather and were more decorated as required by the high status of this noble pastime.

Underwear. Braies (*bracis*) of bishop's follower Herbord were bought for 11d. An undertunic and braies were bought together for 19d for another member of the retinue Conrad the Bohemian. A servants's undertunic (*camisia*) was worth 5d.

Tunics. These came in different price categories. The cheaper ones cost 63-73d, which is already well above the known prices of peasants' clothing. Such tunics were given to messengers or lower-status servants. Higher-status envoys and retinue members were endowed with tunics worth 240-336d.

Hats. Civil hats (*pilleis*) cost 6d apiece.

Ecclesiastical clothing. Ecclesiastical caps (*birretta*) came at a range of prices, from 43d for at least two (mentioned in plural), to 60d for one cap. An unknown number of them were also bought for 444d. A surcingle (ecclesiastical belt) was worth 48d. The bishop's mantle required sandal silk and *brunetto* fabrics worth 872d together. *Soccania*, probably ecclesiastical shoes with gems and embroidery, were priced at a staggering 3132-3276d. Some of the more expensive tunics mentioned above could also be part of ecclesiastical attire.

Cloaks/coats. Rich and warm outer garments were expensive and varied widely in price. A short cloak (*scapruno*), probably unlined, could be as cheap as 31-50d. Two cloaks with hoods were

bought for 147d, although this includes certain “bishop’s clothes”. Another *schapruno* worth 336d (must have been fur-lined) was awarded to messenger Burchard, probably a very rich gift in return for his good service. A gift to Walther von der Vogelweide of 150d was intended for a fur-lined cloak (*pellicio*) as well. That was a relatively expensive item, as Wolfger bought himself cloaks for 120d and 125d. The most expensive one, a raincoat (*pallio pluvioli*) was also bishop’s, priced at 375d. Separate pelts were also bought, apparently to be sewn onto existing clothing during the trip; “various skins for lining the brothers’ habits” (*pro variis pelliculis ad furrendam cucullam*) were bought for 120d, probably when the weather turned to the worse in the autumn of 1203. Finally, 107d was spent on “2 fox pelts and 15 various other pelts”.

3.2.4 Containers

Bags. Bigger bags (*sacco*) were bought for 10d or 12d apiece, implying these were bigger leather bags – quite possibly to keep the money in various currencies, but possibly also used for other goods. A bag for pepper cost 25d – probably very ornate as required by the expensive contents!

Chests/boxes. A “small box” was bought for 12d, although this includes the cryptic “cutting of silver” – perhaps some silver paneling on the same, although the price is not sufficiently high for such decoration. A knife box/container was repaired for 48d – evidently a quality item, and once again including the “cutting of silver”. A chest (*cista*) cost 21d. Special chests carried by the beasts of burden (an unknown quantity) were worth 11d, implying these were simple and robust containers.

3.2.5 Saddles and saddlecloths

Saddles. These were extremely varied in price and, by implication, quality. Saddles (*sella*) were bought for 6d, 24d, 32d, 150d (including the repair of an old one), and 720d. This represents the range from a robust saddle for everyday use by the servants, to a decorated masterpiece probably used by the bishop himself. The assembly/re-strapping of a saddle cost 10d.

Saddlecloths. These cost 4d apiece. 70d was once spent on an unspecified number of basic chairs and benches. A saddlecloth (*subsellium*) for an status saddle cost 72d, though a cheaper one costing 8d is recorded as well.

3.2.6 Swords

Both regular swords for arming the retinue (81d spent on two swords, one of them given to bishop’s servant Wido), as well as ornate weapons intended as gifts (240d and whole 2412d!) The latter ones must have been decorated; the one worth a pound could be gilded and/or silvered, perhaps also with tooled leather belt and/or scabbard, whereas the sword bought for an astronomical price in excess of ten pounds must have been studded with gems. This is the

highest price for a sword I have ever seen. This shows how much high-status weapons cost – those which would make a truly royal gift.

3.2.7 Jewelry, gold and silver items

A drinking cup (entered in the original as *cifo*, i.e. skyphos) worth 5040d, or 21 talent in Veronese coins, was the most expensive item purchased on the trip apart from a palfrey (below). 21 talents, or roughly 21 pound of silver, weight over 9.5 kg, while a drinking cup couldn't possibly weight more than 1 kg. Assuming therefore that the raw silver cost 2 talents, and the work of a goldsmith, say, another 2 talents, the remaining 17 pounds or so could only be contributed by the gemstones set in the cup (and maybe gilding?) So, a very rich drinking vessel. Interestingly, 16d was spent on “making even (*planando*) a silver cup”. Additionally, the bishop was constantly maintaining and acquiring new rings. 324d was spent on a new ring and the polishing of a topaz (presumably set in the same ring). 5d was spent on setting a gem in a ring. 72d, and later 84d, was spent on the fixing of two rings.

3.2.8 Horses and mules

Horses were expensive, as is well known. The prices did vary, however. A horse was bought for 80d – probably a beast of burden; another – for 238d, third – for 2640d, while the final horse cost an impressive 9600d – Engilschalch's palfrey, as they put it. These figures indicate the extremely wide differences in the horse quality and prestige. 800d was spent on an unknown number of donkeys, when the retinue needed extra luggage-carrying capacity.

3.2.9 Miscellaneous

A few odd entries shed light on the Bishop's pastimes during the trip. A man was paid 240d for bringing ivory die (or more dice) to the bishop. Curiously, 18d spent on gambling are also mentioned in the accounts! A book bought from a gentleman in Gozensaz was worth the same 240d. However, besides reading and gambling, the bishop's retinue still had to perform their ecclesiastical duties, hence a purchase of chrism which cost 62d (together with cherries, but the latter must have made a minor fraction of that sum). Very special are the two entries about the purchase of medicines: once, a medicine for the farrier's leg (*pro medicinis ad crus marschalci*) was bought for 12d, and another time, 24d was spent on laxative – medieval nobility was into heavy foods!

3.3 Daily expenses

As distinct from the purchases in the previous section, we may list the expenses on daily necessities, food, services and the such, and derive a tentative budget for an “average day”.

3.3.1 Food

The biggest issue with these accounts that it is impossible to separate the food and drink expenses between those consumed eaten by the retinue and those given in alms or consumed by guests. Although bread in alms at 48-96 d/day is recorded on a few days after the Ascension Day of 1204, the records otherwise do not draw the distinction between the alms and non-alms bread.

Food and drink bills increased sharply around Easter of 1204, apparently reflecting the extra food required to satiate the hunger of the many guests and paupers. The maximum daily spending during that holiday was put at 2810d, given as a sum of food, bread and drinks. The second most expensive day saw 744d spent in bread, 480d in wine, and 1200 in horse fodder. Since the horse fodder also required a bigger than usual spending, these provisions were therefore intended to last for a few days and maybe cover the fodder for the guests. Outside of the festive seasons, food and drink cost several times less.

Although only a few food items are mentioned specifically, but these reveal the tastes of our bishop and his friends. For some reason, chicken (2d apiece) and payments to fowlers were entered separately from other food on a few occasions. Also separate are the purchases of turnips, pears, fish, cherries, fruits, at 4-12d each, and 24d worth of deer milk (maybe used as medicine?). A hunter received 24d once - perhaps a payment for game meat, but the sum isn't particularly large. Of course, the bishop had to maintain his status by buying saffron with 564-566d a couple of times, and once saffron together with pepper (price unreadable). A bag for pepper was mentioned above.

3.3.2 Services

The retinue used a broader range of services than one would imagine. First, they did laundry and used baths on nearly every stop. Additionally, barber for the bishop and bloodletters are also mentioned. Guards were employed, possibly meaning additional men hired locally. Several times, boat and ship crews were paid to transport the retinue and food via the rivers. Once, a "ship to Bologna" was hired for 159d, which may imply that the entire retinue could fit on a single ship. Tolls were paid, but these were either small ("4d at the bridge", I assume a toll for crossing), heavy (792d) or even heavier (1492d). Often, they had tailors, sewers and "garment cutters" change the size and mend various clothes. Finally, the courtyard of their accommodation was cleaned – not for free! – this, too, once cost the bishop a whole 48d.

3.3.3 Horses

Horses incurred hefty expenses and required constant care. Horseshoes were bought on an almost daily basis, typically at 2-26d per day (average 9d), shodding cost another 8-30d to which the lord's horse added a further 2-8d. Reins, horse belts, bridles, and tack in general, were bought and repaired (this was relatively inexpensive). A new muzzle for the bishop's horse was bought with 8d.

3.4 Messengers

It seems that the bishop was incessantly sending or receiving messengers and envoys. They received allowances of 4-240d, which probably depended on many factors including the social status of the messenger, the importance/urgency of a message, the distance, road conditions and weather. In most cases, the term *nuncius* is used to describe the messenger, while *garcio* (servant) delivered the message only sometimes, and *cursor* is mentioned only once.

3.5 Performers

The performers occupy a special place in the records. Payments to entertainers of all sorts are every frequent. Jongleurs, actors, singers, child singers, fiddlers, jugglers with knives, mimes, minstrels, descant-singers and “Pope’s singers” can be found in the text. These received 5-240d per person – a very wide range, probably dependent on the quality of the performance. The famous Walther von der Vogelweide was given 150d (five “long shillings”) to buy a fur-lined cloak; this was not the highest recorded payment to an entertainer, despite his fame. Walther, however, was the only one mentioned by his full name; the jugglers Gilioto and Flordamor were the two others who had the honour of being so remembered.

3.6 Approximate daily budget

The records contain an unbroken sequence of about three weeks in when the food, drink and fodder expenses were entered daily, which provide some grounds for deriving a typical daily budget. To this, we may add the minor but regular expenses which are mentioned several times throughout the text. Some of these are my guesses and attempts to generalize the not-so-well organized accounts, but the overall picture should be approximately correct and representative.

The wages of “staff” (cook, barber, falconer, guards, personal servants, farriers, cellarers, laundresses, sailors, bathkeepers, bloodletters, carpenters, smiths, goldsmiths, sailors, etc.) comprise a minor fraction of the daily total – about 50d/day. Some of them were part of the retinue; others were hired on the way. For instance, bishop’s own sailors are mentioned. Accommodation of the bishop and the more important of his associates incurred an estimated 100d/day, about 6d/day for the rent of a servants’ room – compare with stables were much more expensive at around 60 per day. The greater part of the daily budget consisted of bread and other food and wine, about 480d together. Horse fodder was surprisingly expensive, adding about 240d. The maintenance of Bishop’s and others’ horses (horseshoes, shodding, tack maintenance, cleaning and the such) cost about 22 per day. Wax and light wicks (to make candles) added a noticeable 54d, on average – although this understandably varied a lot between winter and summer. The bishop frequently employed or received messengers and envoys (40d/day, on average) and performers (100d/day). Various repairs were done on a nearly daily basis, amounting to about 36d per day.

These average expenses illustrate a more expensive day in terms of money spent on necessities, as certain items may be missing on some days. On the other hand, on other days extra purchases

may have been required. Therefore, I estimate the relative uncertainty on these figures at about 50%.

Table 1. Approximate daily budget.

Sum (d)	Expense
2	master cook (<i>magistro coquine</i>)
3	barber for the Bishop (<i>rasorius/barbe</i>)
3	maintenance of Bishop's horse (<i>equis Episcopi</i>)
4	light wicks (<i>lieno</i>) (for the making of candles)
5	falconer (<i>falconarius</i>)
6	guards (<i>vigili</i>)
6	rent of servants' room
6	servant (<i>servo domini episcopi</i>)
6	farrier (<i>marschalcus</i>)
9	laundry (<i>lotrici</i>)
9	horseshoes (<i>ferramentis</i>) and shodding (<i>sufferando</i>)
10	saffron and pepper (<i>safrano, piper</i>)
10	treats (pears, fruits, cherries)
10	for the stables (<i>equis camere</i>) - wages of the grooms?
13	bathing, to the bath keeper (<i>balneator</i>) and bloodletters (<i>minutori</i>)
36	random tasks in preparation/repair of clothes, furniture, tableclothes, rings, etc.
40	to an envoy/messenger (<i>nuncius/cursor</i>)
50	for wax (<i>cera</i>) [for the making of wax candles]
60	stables (<i>pro stabulatum</i>) - for the rent of stables
72	drink (<i>potu</i>)
100	for a performance of a juggler/mime/actor/singer/fiddler etc.
120	accommodation (<i>hospitium</i>)
120	bread (<i>pane</i>)
120	wine (<i>vino</i>)
240	food (<i>coquina</i>)
240	horse and donkey fodder (<i>pabulo/gramine/freno</i>)
1300	TOTAL = 5.4 talents/day

4. General overview of the budget

Table 2. Approximate overall budget of the trip lasting for several months.

sum (d)	% of total	category	comments
36934	22%	Gifts	Order of magnitude estimate: 100 days of active travel * 1000d/day
27391	16%	Purchases	
100,000	59%	Food, services, necessities, repair	
1521	1%	Messengers	
4010	2%	Performers	
169,856	100%	Total	

As one can see from Table 2, a truly astronomical sum was spent in the trip which lasted several months in 1203-1204. About 38% of the total is comprised of money spent on gifts and purchases, which sum up to about 65,545 pennies, or 269 talents. The expenditure on food, services, necessities and repair may be overestimated as stated earlier, but in my opinion the budget couldn't have been less than 100,000d, and could possibly amount to 200,000d or over (416-832 talents, approximately equal to pounds sterling). This must have been a significant extra burden on bishop Wolfger's treasury. Such an estimate is of the same order of magnitude as annual income of an (ecclesiastical or lay) prince at the time – high, but not impossible.

One cannot help but wonder how the funds were transported, as all payments were made in cash which had to be constantly at hand. The low estimate of 416 talents would weigh a total of about 200 kg! They must have used a separate cart for the specific purpose of carrying the coins. Also, since 13 different currencies were used in the trip, they needed to be divided into separate bags (remember the purchase of money bags); a full-time treasurer would have been required to take care of all that, although such is not mentioned explicitly in the text. A sizeable group of guards would have been required – in fact, these are mentioned many times, although their services seem to have been cheap.

5. Translated original entries

Glossary

d - *denarius* (penny), a small silver coin, about 2g in weight

talent = 240d - approximately the same as pound sterling (*libra*) in terms of silver weight.

Libra (L) also consisted of 240 pennies.

shilling = 12d (also called "short shilling")

long shilling = 30d

mark = 2/3 talent = 160d

Bon., Veron., mezan., Sen., Imper., Frisac. - the various regional currencies used by the retinue as they were traveling. The current work does not take into account the exchange rates; the pennies of different mint did not differ significantly, so exchange rates are omitted for simplicity.

Sum (d)	GIFTS
2	2d – to two sick people (<i>infirmis</i>)
6	6d – to a poor child (<i>paupercule</i>)
12	12d to a cleric
12	12d – to a cleric
12	12d to a "wretched priest" (<i>lodderphasso</i>)
12	12d to an oblearius (church official distributing <i>oblearii</i>)
12	1s – to a scholar from San Mauritio
12	1s – to two boys
12	1s – to a scholar from Westphalia
12	to a naked boy (<i>nudo garcioni</i>)
12	To the barber, for boots/leggings, a shilling
18	1s – to a poor man; 6d - to other paupers
24	2s for an old pauper
24	24d to a "bald apostate from Ensdorf" (<i>calvo apostate de Enstorf</i>)
24	2s – to a pilgrim
24	2s Bon. – to a vagrant
24	2s mezan. – to a pilgrim, 3s mezan. to pilgrim
24	2S Veron. – to two grey monks
24	2s – to two French people (<i>francigenis</i>)
24	2 s Bon. To an old man (<i>vago</i>)
30	30d to an old scholar
30	30d – to a blind man (<i>ceco</i>)
30	2 short shillings – to an old pauper
30	To an itinerant pilgrim, 30d (<i>wallero girovago</i>)
36	3s – to a crusader, for provisions
36	3s – to a poor crusader from Normandy
36	36d – to the royal cellarer (<i>spisarius</i>)
40	To a monk, 40d
60	60d - to a brother [monk]

60	60d – to the saddler? (<i>sellator</i>) from Treveren
60	60d – to an old man
60	2 long shillings - to a servant
60	5s to a "wretched priest"/vagrant (<i>lodderpasso</i>)
60	5s – to a nun (<i>monialibus</i>) from Eboracum
64	64d – to two pilgrims
66	66d – for a tunic and a short cloak (<i>scaprano</i>) to the servant/messenger from Rome
70	70d for a tunic to...
80	Half a mark – to a fat Saxon scolar wearing black clothes
80	0.5 mark – to a blond Saxon in black clothes
84	7s – to a poor cleric
120	0.5L to a cleric
120	0.5L – to the presbyter
144	0.5L + 24d. Frisac. - to a Syrian (<i>Siriis</i>)
240	1L – to a parish priest
240	1L (+ wax tablet) - To a parish priest
240	1L to a Bowman (<i>sagittarius</i>)
240	1L to magister of St. Florian
240	1L to lord Crafton's steward
240	1L to the canonic of Niwemburgh
240	1L mezan. – to a knight
240	1L - to Roland, who used to be a servant of the Bishop
240	1L – to a Bowman (<i>sagittario</i>)
240	For a sword, which was given to the host from Florence, 20 shillings
250	1L + 10d worth of linen cloth - to a dean
276	23 sol. Veron – to a Hungarian for a tunic
317	2 Frisach marks – for the Lord Richoro de Steudentorf
317	2 marks – to the canonicus for accommodation (<i>hospitio nostro</i>)
336	28 sol. Frisach. - to an abbot
336	28 sol. Veron. – to a scholar for a tunic
480	2L – parish priest
480	2L – to the knight Heinrich <i>Suevo</i> (the Swabian)
480	2L to Lord Conrad de Asparne
480	2L to bishop's son
480	2L – to lord Werner von Aldenhoven
480	2L – to the old bloodletter of the duke Luipold (<i>minutori antiqui</i>)
480	2L Veron. – to two youths (<i>iuvenibus</i>) from Aquilea
720	3L – to dean (old friendship)
960	6 marks – to the monks of Cheisheim
1200	5L – to a provost
2400	On the day of Pentecost, to the monks when the lord bishop was the celebrant, 10 talents Veronese
2400	At the pass, sent by Guido to the man from Parma who had loaned [us] Paduan mezanini, for our gratitude, 10 talents Veronese

2500	10 L – to a cellarer (old friendship)
2620	10.5L to a monk- monastery official (officius)
5160	To the lord Duoring
9600	40L – to Guido de Munzun and the Bishop's patron (<i>patrino episcopi</i>)
36934	total = 154 talents

Sum (d) PURCHASES

3	3d for a dagger/knife (<i>cultello</i>) of magister H.
3	3d for a knife
3	3d for whips (<i>corrigiis</i>) and horse reins (<i>bulgas</i>)
3	3d for the shoes of master Heinrich
3	3d for brother Heinrich's belt
3	3d – for small metal parts (?) (<i>ferruncis</i>)
3	for a case/cover for razors 3d
4	4d – for bishop's gloves
4	4d for a bench (<i>subsellio</i>)
4	4d for Bishop's gloves
4	4d for William's shoes
4	4d for the shoes of the room servant boy (<i>garciunculi in camera</i>)
4	4d – for two gloves
4	4d – for a bench
4	2d, 2d - ropes
5	5d for a pair of shoes
5	5d for the shoes of the servant who drives the beasts of burden (<i>pro calciis garcionis , qui vehit soumarium</i>)
5	5d – for wallets/small money bags? (<i>bursis</i>)
5	5d Frisac. – to Widon's servant for an undertunic (<i>camisia</i>)
6	6d – for a falconry glove
6	6d Frisac – for a saddle (<i>sella</i>)
7	7d – for the threads for the bishop's clothes
7	7d for bishop's mattress (<i>culcitra</i>)
7	7d – for Herbordo's leggings/riding boots (<i>bracis</i>)
7	For purses/moneybags, 7d
8	8d for two bottles/jugs (<i>lagenas</i>)
8	8d – falconry gloves
8	for cloth for covering the queen of Bohemia's saddle, 8d
8	For grease/fat for shoes, 8d (<i>pingui pro calciis</i>)
10	10d for a sack/bag/money bag? (<i>sacco</i>)
10	10d for the assembly/restrapping (<i>liganda</i>) of brother Heinrich's saddle
11	11d to Normanno for gloves, hat (<i>pilleo</i>) and mitra
11	10d, 12d, for a bag (<i>sacco</i>)
11	11d – for braies (<i>bracis</i> , for Herbord)
11	11d for travel chests (chests carried by the beasts of burden, <i>soumscriniis</i>)

12	12d for two hats (<i>pilleis</i>)
12	12d for shoes (<i>calcii</i>)
12	12d for Widon's shoes
12	12d – for two hoods/capes (<i>pilleis</i>)
12	12d for fishing rods/hooks (<i>hamis ad lupos?</i>)
12	12d for the sheaves/scabbards of the razor knives (<i>receptaculis razoriorum</i>)
12	For the cost of cutting silver and for the small box, 12d
15	15d for the purchase and increasing the size of a cape (<i>mantica</i>)
18	18d – for the reins of the beasts of burden
18	18d for light summer shoes (<i>estivalibus</i>) – for Normanno
19	19d for chemise and braies for Conrad the Bohemian
21	21d for a chest (<i>cista</i>)
22	To Andrea for wood for the framing of a house loft/upper floor, 22d (<i>lignis ad tristega</i>)
24	24d “for small things” (<i>pro minutis rebus</i>)
24	24d to the servant of Normanno, for a saddle
24	2S Ratisbon. – for a purse/money bag (<i>bursa</i>)
26	26d for shoes for Normanno
28	28d Veron. – for the spurs of the scholar Pilgrim (<i>calcaribus</i>)
29	29d for light summer shoes (<i>estivalibus</i>) – for Heinrich
30	30d for fishing rods/hooks (<i>hamis</i>)
31	31d for a short cloak (<i>schapruno</i>) – to Ulrich, servant of Brother Heinrich
31	31d For brother Heinricho for the linen
32	32d for a saddle (<i>sella</i>)
36	12d, 12d, 12d, for parchment
37	3d, 2d, 12d, 5d, 6d, 4d, 4d, for light wicks (<i>lieno</i>)
43	43d. – for two hats (<i>birrettis</i>)
48	For a surcingle, 4 shillings Veronese
51	51d – to Gerhard for falconry gloves
54	For covering the saddle (i.e. saddle cloth?) which was sent to the queen of Bohemia and for other items of apparel
60	5s – for a hat (<i>birretta</i>)
60	60d Ratisbon. – for linen cloth
60	5s Bon. for a hat/beret (<i>birretta</i>)
62	62d for bishop's shoes (<i>caligi</i>)
62	62d – for bishop's shoes
62	For chrim and cherries, 5 shillings and 2d Veronese
70	70d for a tunic
70	70d – for the purchase of saddlecloths and saddles
72	6s Veron. – for two belts (<i>cingulis</i>), of the butler and brother Heinrich
72	72d for the purchase of the cloth for magister Heinrichus to place on the saddle
73	73d for Normanno's tunic
80	0.5 marc – for a horse
81	81d – for two swords, one of which belongs to Wido

101	3 long shillings + 11d - for 2 new cloaks of Wido and Normanno
107	107d – for 2 fox pelts + 15 various other pelts
120	0.5L for Bishop's fur-lined coat
120	0.5L for various skins for lining the monks' habits <i>pro variis pelliculis ad furrendam cucullam</i>
125	0.5L + 5d. for own lined coat (<i>pellicio</i>)
147	0.5L + 27d – two cloaks with hoods and Bishop's clothes
150	5 long shillings for repair of an old saddle and the purchase of one new saddle
238	1.5 marks for a horse
240	1L – for a book to one gentleman in Gozzensaz. (<i>cuidam domine pro libello</i>)
240	1L – for Pilgrim's tunic
240	1L - To the man who brought the ivory die/dice to the bishop
240	For a sword, which was given to the host from Florence, 20 shillings
300	25s – to Gerhard for a tunic
324	27s – for the purchase of Bishop's ring and the polishing of the topaz (<i>thopaziis</i>);
336	28 sol. Veron. – for the cloak (<i>schapruno</i>) of the messenger (<i>cursoris</i>) Burchard
375	12.5 long shillings for bishop's raincoat (<i>pallio pluviali</i>)
384	32s – for two silken belts of the Bishop (<i>sericinis cingulis</i>)
444	37s Veron. – for the hats (<i>birrettis</i>)
566	47 shillings Sen. + 2d – for saffron
720	3L Veron – for a saddle
800	5 marks for the purchase of donkeys (<i>pro emendis asinis</i>)
872	32 imperial shillings – for sandal silk for the Bishop's mantle (<i>zindalo ad failam</i>); for <i>brunetto</i> (thin, dark fabric) for the same mantle, 2L + 8 imperial shillings
1864	0.5L, 62d, 0.5L+40d, 0.5L, 14d, 51d, 3 long shillings, 0.5L+20d, 72d, 80d, 74d, 49d, 77d, 58d, 72d, 0.5L, 62d, 0.5L + 15d, 48d, 240, for wax
2412	10L + 1s Veron. – for the sword to scholar Pilgrim
2640	11L Veron. – for a horse
3132	13L + 1s Veron. – for Gernodo's ecclesiastical boots (?) (<i>soccania</i>)
3276	14L minus 7s. Veron. – for Normanno's ecclesiastical boots (?) (<i>soccania</i>)
5040	21 L Veron. – for a silver drinking cup (<i>argenteo cifo</i>) - probably set with gems!!
9600	For Engelschalch's palfrey, 40 talents Veronese
27391	total = 153 talents

Sum (d) V FOOD

2	2d for a chicken
2	2d to the master cook (<i>magistro coquine</i>)
2	2d for the cellarer (keeper of the food stores, <i>spisarius</i>) Arnold
4	4d for turnips
6	6d for the cooks (<i>cocis</i>)
7	7d for the pears (<i>piris</i>)
8	8d – fish
12	12d, 12d – for cherries
12	1s Veron for fruits
24	Brother Heinrich at Gottweig gave to a hunter from ?Batavia, 24d

24	2s- for deer milk (<i>lacte cervi</i>)
24	2s Veron. – for laxative
25	25d – for a bag for pepper
33	33d – for the kitchen/food
47	20s + 7s in Vienna coins – to the kitchen (coquinam); 0.5L for bread; 6 long shillings -8d for drink; 1L +7d for fodder; 51d – for the wages (to the hired workers? <i>vadiis</i>)
60	60d to a fowler (chicken keeper, aucupi)
564	47s – for saffron
566	47 shillings Sen. + 2d – for saffron Saffron and pepper bought together (price unreadable)

Sum (d) A TYPICAL DAY – EXEMPLARY ENTRIES

	5L + 5 short Venetian shillings – for the kitchen; 3L + 2s – for bread; 2.5L – for the wine; 5L + 20d for the fodder;
	Day 5, same place, at lunch (<i>in prandio</i>): 5L 5s kitchen; 42s bread; 30s wine; hay 5s; 5s <i>pro lectis</i> ; 5s + 2d Frisac +2d Ratisbon. to the host for the stables (<i>hospiti pro stabulato</i>); 13s for miscellaneous (horses, clothes and benches).
	56d - For the kitchen; 39d – for wine; 17d – for the hay; 9d – for the accommodation (<i>dormitionis</i>); 9d - for the horseshoes, laundry and bathing; 19d - to the patriarch's <i>conditoribus</i> (?) for food and drink; 8d – to the butler (<i>pincerne</i>).
	3L - To the kitchen; 2L+30d bread; 3L+30d wine; 4.5L for fodder;
	4L+6s – Kitchen; 2L+6s bread; 2L+8s wine; 2L+17s fodder; 12s hay
	75d – for bread/food (<i>pane</i>); 31d Frisac. – for wine; 62d – for fodder.
2810	12L minus 70d – to the kitchen for the food, bread and drinks (ad coquinam et panem et pabulum et potum) NOTE: at/near easter

Sum (d) SERVICES, REPAIR

2	2d Frisac. – to the guards (vigili)
2	2d- for repairing Bishop's cloak (<i>pellibus</i>)
3	3d for repair of tablecloths
3.5	3d, 4d – barber (<i>barbe</i>)
4	to the garment cutter, 4d
4	For drink for the cutters, 4d
4	4d - for stitching/sewing ecclesiastical boots (?) (<i>socania</i>)
4	4d - to the garment cutter (<i>incisori vestibus</i>); 4d - For drink for the cutters (<i>incisoribus potu</i>)
4	4d - at the bridge (toll?)
5	5d - For setting a gem in a ring (<i>pro reponenda gemma in anulum</i>)
6	6d - To the farrier (<i>marschalco</i>)
6	6d for the servant's room (rent)
7	To the washerwoman for washing ? and ?linen, 7d (<i>pro lavando (?) et lieno</i>)
7	7d for servants' necessities
9	10d, 15d, 7d, 10d, 3d, for laundresses (for washing the clothes)
12	12 – to the bloodletters/bathmaids in the baths (<i>minutori in estuario</i>); 8d for other bath keepers (<i>balneatori</i>)
12	12d – to a wood turner (<i>tornator</i>)
12	1s August. – to a man who ran in the night to explore (investigate) the lower bridge at Lici

(Cuidam , qui ad explorandum inferiorem Lici pontem de nocte cucurrit)

12	12d – for a small boat
12	1s – for the medicine for the farrier's leg (<i>pro medicinis ad crus marschalci</i>)
13	15d, 12d – to bath-keeper (<i>balneator</i>)
16	16s – to the sailors (<i>naute</i>)
16	16d Frisac. – for making even (<i>pro planando</i> , repairing) a silver cup (<i>argenteo cifo</i>)
16	16d - to Bishop's silors (<i>naute episcopi</i>) - accompanies the Bologna ship record above.
18	12d, 3d, 3d to a servant (<i>garcio</i>)
18	For gaming/gambling, 18d Ratisbon
24	2s Veron. – guards
28	To the lord Otto, for sending apparel ahead to Florence, 28d
30	For the woodcutters, 30d (<i>Succisoribus silve</i>)
34	34d – for the sailors (<i>naute</i>)
34	34d – for wages and guards (<i>pro vadiis et vigilibus</i>)
41	3d, 3d, 6d, 4d, 10d, 10d, 2d, 6d, to the falconer
43	30d, 6d, 3 long shillings+3d, – for sailors (<i>naute</i>)
48	for cleaning the courtyard (<i>pro purganda curia</i>) 4s
48	For cutting(?) silver and for the repair of the knife box/container, 4 shillings
60	To the sewers/stitchers, 5 shillings Veronese
60	60d – for those, who prepared Bishop's clothes
60	60d – to the guards (<i>vigilibus</i>)
60	60d to the magister Conrad de Teutonico, for hospitality (<i>hospitali</i>)
60	For valuation of a cart, 5 shillings
70	To an innkeeper to calm his anger, and to the watchmen, 6 shillings minus 2d (?)
72	6s – for the repair of two rings
74	7s Bon. – for preparation of the presbyter's clothes
84	7s - for repair of two rings
138	For food brought with us on the ship, 11 shillings and 6d
159	13s +3d - for the ship to Bologna (from Ferrara? About 40 km straight distance)
288	For bringing Pilgrim's saddle valued at 4 shillings Veronese. To someone so that he would be willing to take back his bridle/(horse) harness, 1 talent Veronese
720	3L – to the lord canonic, for the reception
792	There we gave in tolls/customs duty, 3 talents and 6 shillings in Bolognese money
1492	6L + 5 long shillnigs – 8d : to the toll collector at Ashe
3196	At Heilsbronn, sent to the innkeeper at Wurzburg, 20 marks
7672	At the Curia, 48 marks (first record) (<i>In curiam .xLviiij, marc</i>)
7672	At the Curia, 48 marks (second record) (<i>In curiam .xLviiij, marc</i>)
23286.5	total = 97 talents

Sum (d) HORSE MAINTENANCE

9	13d, 4d, 2d, 26d, 10d, 6d, 2d, – for horseshoes
6.5	3d, 10d – for hay and horseshoes
10	10d for horse fodder and shodding nails

60	60d for horse fodder (<i>pabulo</i>)
5	5d – for horseshoes
2	2d – for repairing Bishop's reins (<i>freno</i>)
2	2d – for horse belts (saddle parts?) (<i>cinculis equinis</i>)
5	5d – for bridle/ horse tack (<i>freno</i>)
6	6d- for two reins (<i>habenis</i>)
8	8d for leather muzzle for Bishop's palfrey (<i>capistro ad palefridam</i>)
3	4d, 4d, 3d, 2d, – Bishop's horse
6	2d, 8d, for shodding the Bishop's horse
10.5	6d, 8d, 5d, 30d, 12d, – stables (<i>equis camere</i>)

Sum (d) MESSENGERS

4	4d for a messenger (<i>cursor</i>)
6	6d. to the messenger of Zahringen for the purchase of (riding) leggings (<i>ocreas</i>)
12	For the messenger (<i>nuncius</i>) from Bohemia 12d.
12	12d – to a messenger from Bohemia
24	24d – messenger (<i>nuncio</i>) from Stritwisen
24	2s for the messenger (<i>nuncius</i>) from Pattavia, who brought a belt? Puppy? (<i>catulum</i>)
28	28d – to a messenger (<i>nuncio</i>) from Bohemia
30	30d for messenger (<i>nuncio</i>) from Bohemia
40	40d – for the servant (messenger), who went to the duke of Bavaria
40	40d to a servant (<i>garcioni</i>) who ran [with a message] to the duke of Bavaria
48	4s – to the messengers of the Magdeburg Archbishop and the Marquis of Landsberg
50	50d – to a servant (<i>garcioni</i> , messenger?) of the Pope
60	60d for the messenger of the archbishop of Mainz
60	60d to the Archbishop's messenger <i>nuncio</i>
63	For the messenger (<i>nuncius</i>) of the Hungarian King 63d. for a tunic
120	0.5L – to a messenger from Constantinople
180	6 long shillings to Royal messenger <i>nuncius</i>
240	1L to a messenger (<i>nuncius</i>) of the King and Marquis of Landsberg
240	1L to a messenger (<i>nuncius</i>) of the King and Marquis of Landsberg
240	1L to the messenger of the king Philip and Marquis of Landsberg
1521	total = 6.3 talents

Sum (d) PERFORMERS

5	5d – to a female singer (<i>cantatrici</i>)
12	to a juggler
12	to a juggler
12	1s – to other actors
12	1s – to a juggler
24	24d – to three jugglers
24	2s – to a child singer (<i>puellis cantatribus</i>)
24	2s to another mime

24	2s – to a fiddler (<i>gigarius</i>)
30	to a juggler
30	30d - To the bald player/actor
36	3s – to a juggler
48	4s – to jugglers
60	5 shillings - to a singer (<i>vociferatori</i>)
60	5 shillings <i>mezanorum</i> - to an old juggler in a red cotta
60	5s – to a juggler
60	5 shillings - to the mime called Gilioto
60	5 s veron. – to a singing boy/girl (<i>puellus cantantibus</i>)
60	5s Veron. - to a mime
60	5s – to the juggler called Gilioto
60	5 shillings <i>mezanorum</i> to a female singer (<i>cuidam cantatrici</i>)
92	7s + 6d – to two singers and one juggler
120	10s - for one with a fiddle (<i>giga</i>) and his/her associate
120	0.5L of Verona – to a mime
120	0.5L – to a French with a fiddle and his (her?) associate
120	0.5 L to an actor from Lombardy (<i>istrioni</i>)
120	0.5L Veron – to a juggler
150	5 long shillings to the minstrel (<i>cantor</i>) <i>WALTHERO de VOGELWEIDE</i> , for a fur-lined cloak (<i>pellicium</i>)
240	1L Bononian – to a juggler called Flordamor
240	1L – to an old singer (<i>vetulo discantori</i>) and his son
240	1L Veron. - to a juggler with a dagger (<i>joculatori cum cultellis</i>)
240	1L – to a juggler with daggers (<i>joculatori cum cultellis</i>)
240	1L – to Pope's singer (?) (<i>cantoribus pape</i>)
240	To the lord pope's descant-singers, a talent (<i>discantores</i>)
480	2L to four jugglers (<i>quatuor jocularibus</i>)
480	2L – to two actors (<i>duobus istrionibus</i>)
4010	total = 16.7 talents